

Documenting digital families – the methodology of PlatFAMs

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How are digital platforms embedded in the lives and practices of modern families? ‘*Platforming Families: Tracing digital transformations in everyday life across generations (PlatFAMs)*’ researches three generation families in Estonia, Norway, Romania, Spain, the UK and Poland.

During 2024 each team included in the PlatFAMs project collected the qualitative data that will aid us in understanding how families today navigate in their every day lives with digital devices, digital media, apps and platforms. In this short paper we will highlight methodological aspects of interest to others which gives insight into what contemporary family life across generations looks like, in a number of European countries.

What we have done so far

In our review of existing research (Erstad et al 2024), we found relatively little research including three generations of informants, let alone from the same families. In all, the PlatFAMs project has interviewed 312 grandparents (100), parents (104) and children/teens (108) from the six countries.

Our sample

We have included more than 100 families in our study. During recruitment, each team worked hard to include all types of families, and get a good balance of genders, educational levels and ethnicity reflecting the national overall composition. Our youngest participant is 7 ½ years old, and our oldest was 84. Most interviews were face-to-face.

The PlatFAMs total sample (prelim)

312 participants from 104 families

First round – Individual interviews

Our first round of semi-structured interviews included one child (aged 8-17 years), one parent and one grandparent from each family. The 1-2 hour interviews focused on platform navigation and negotiation, relationality, future-making, and media childhoods, also including practical tasks (platform usage mapping and family app design). To inspire our participants to talk about navigating apps, digital platforms, and algorithms in their daily life, we presented them with a number of platform logos, and invited them to describe their use and sort them: which would they rather leave behind, which would they absolutely need to bring with them into the future?

Second round – Family group interviews and participatory methods

Our second round of interviews includes a selected sample of families for a family interview, also including family members not included in the first round. This data material of 12+ family interviews are aimed at understanding how family dynamics and relationships interact with platform use, and families' thoughts about technological development in the future.

One fun task is for them to bring a media or family communication related object to the table and explain what this represents in their life story. We have seen old house telephones, teen magazines, toy cars and a walk man, and talked about telegrams. Our generations represent different media generations. In one instance, the middle generation described themselves as a 'transition generation', representing both the 'old' offline world and the 'new' online world including cell phones and internet.

The other task we presented for our families were to design 'The perfect family app' for their family together. In response to the challenge of designing the perfect family app, one family brainstormed about activities they would like to do together. Play football golf with the whole family, DIY together, eat a long breakfast, go to a café and other offline activities needed coordination – The perfect app for this family was designed as a calendar/notice board to accommodate everyone's wishes. Other families have designed a perfect 'cooking together' app, or a coordination app including a "hologram"/virtual reality option for family members who wanted to be in the same room to interact.

Participatory methods: This is a drawing made by one interviewee – 14-year-old “Frida” from Norway. Her drawing shows herself with her mom, shopping clothes online from the living room sofa. Also present is her dad, scrolling through Facebook. In the adjacent room, her twin sisters are sitting together enjoying horse videos on YouTube. Family members together, but doing different activities – a typical family situation today?

Platforms and family life – a new book!

In collaboration with colleagues at the Centre for Research on the Digital Child in Australia, PlatFAMs has published [this open access book](#). Here we outline how the digital platforms that are part of so many different aspects of commercial and personal life have begun to transform everyday family life. Hopefully, the book will inspire others who investigate the changes that platformization has brought to the routines and interactions of family life. Communication and relationships between generations, new forms of care and togetherness are illustrated by examples from our data.

PlatFAMs moving forward

Completing our individual interviews in 2024, the PlatFAMs researchers are moving into analyses of the data material. The results of these analyses will be presented through publications in special issues of scientific journals, articles in country specific and international journals, news outlets, presentations in conferences etc. Results will be made available through [the PlatFAMs web site](#).

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